

**STUDYING ITS ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECT AFTER PARENTERAL
ADMINISTRATION OF GLUCOSAMINE SULFATE IN POST-TRAUMATIC
GONARTHROSIS**

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Relevance of the topic. At present, doctors engaged in clinical practice in the conservative treatment of arthrosis pay great attention to chondroprotectors. The increase in the number of people who are regularly involved in sports in Uzbekistan has an effect on the increase in the statistics of post-traumatic knee joint arthrosis (gonarthrosis). At the beginning of the pathogenesis of arthrosis of the knee joint lies the inflammation and degenerative disorder of the structure of the joint; parenteral (intramuscular) use of chondroprotector - glucosamine sulfate in order to eliminate pain, inflammation, and limitation of movement, is showing much better results today. Glucosamine comes in 2 forms: glucosamine sulfate and glucosamine hydrochloride. Since the glucosamine hydrochloride molecule is much smaller than the glucosamine sulfate molecule and its absorption is easy, clinical studies have proven that the therapeutic effect is higher in stabilized glucosamine sulfate-containing preparations. In our study, glucosamine sulfate ("Sinarta", intramuscular injection of 2 ml, in one day No.25) was used as a chondroprotector. Glucosamine sulfate ("Sinarta") has a significant anti-inflammatory effect on joints; stimulates the synthesis of type I and II collagens, the amount of which decreases in the skin and tissues with age, improves phosphorus-calcium exchange in the ankle tissue, the synthesis of proteoglycans and synovial fluid, as a result, swelling in the joint decreases and vice versa, the amount of synovial fluid increases and the joint movement becomes easier, pain decreases.

The purpose of the study. Study of the anti-inflammatory effect of parenteral (intramuscular) administration of glucosamine sulfate in post-traumatic gonarthrosis in outpatients.

Research method and material. A study was conducted on 31 patients with the diagnosis of gonarthrosis of the I-II-III degree who were being treated on an outpatient basis in

multidisciplinary and family polyclinics of the city of Termiz. Age of patients: 20-51, 14 women, 17 men. Patients were prescribed "Sinarta", intramuscular injection of 2 ml, in one day No.25. No side effects were observed in patients. X-ray and ultrasound examinations of the knee joints were performed on the Doppler-UZI apparatus.

Research results. 26 out of 31 patients, i.e. 83.8%, who received "Sinarta" intermuscular injection of 2 ml of in one day No.25, movements in the knee joints reached 80-90% (grade I-II gonarthrosis) was restored, in the remaining 5 patients (16.2% - grade III gonarthrosis), movements in the knee joints were restored to 20-30%; it was observed that pain and swelling in the joint decreased in all patients (this was confirmed by Doppler-UZI ultrasound examination).

Summary. According to the results of the research, 26 out of 31 patients, i.e., 83.8% (grade I-II gonarthrosis) who received 2 ml intramuscular injection of "Sinarta" no. 80-90% movement in knee joints was restored, in the remaining 5 patients (16.2% - III-degree gonarthrosis), movement in knee joints was restored up to 20-30%; pain and swelling in the joint decreased in all patients. The reduction of swelling in the joints was also confirmed by the ultrasound examination on the Doppler-UZI device. By this means, the effective anti-inflammatory effect of the chondroprotector - glucosamine sulfate when administered parenterally (intramuscularly) in arthrosis of the knee joint.

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